

STABILIZED MORTAR CONTAINING METAKAOLIN

Iranilza C. da Silva, Universidade Federal de Campina Grande, BR, yrnilzaa@gmail.com
Leane P. B. Sales, Universidade Federal da Paraíba, BR, leanepiscillab@gmail.com
Henrique M. C. de Melo, Universidade Federal da Paraíba, BR, henriquecondedemelo15@gmail.com
Lenimar de A. O. Junior, Universidade Federal da Paraíba, BR, lenimarjr@gmail.com
Aline F. N. de Azerêdo, Universidade Federal da Paraíba, BR, alinefnobrega@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Several residues have potential for use in mortars and concrete, such as wastes from kaolin production (KW). So, this article aimed to study the use of metakaolin (MK) from the KW as partial replacement for Portland cement in stabilized mortars with 10% and 20% content in order to also contribute to the stabilization time. All mixtures were placed in moist environment curing for 28 days after stabilization times (0 and 48 hour). The results showed that the mortar containing 10% of MK showed greater gains in axial compressive strength.

KEYWORDS

Mortars; Stabilization; kaolin residue.

INTRODUCTION

The civil construction sector is constantly looking for solutions that can increase productivity in construction processes without losing quality. Although widely used, conventional mortars are still evidenced for having productivity problems, generating immense waste of materials, high labor time for their preparation and high pathological incidences (FERREIRA, 2016).

One way to improve these aspects is the industrialization of materials, represented by mortars produced in plants and delivered in bagged, bulk, or ready-to-use works, such as stabilized mortars (THOMÉ, 2019). It is noteworthy, however, that this production system is little used and widespread in Brazilian civil construction (PAGNUSSAT, 2012).

Stabilized mortar is a ready-to-use mixture according to its purpose and remains workable for 24 to 72 hours, depending on the dosage of the additive. (MATOS, 2013). According to Carasek (2010), Bauer et al. (2015) and Oliveira (2017) stabilized mortars have very fine-grained cement and sand in their composition, in addition to the use of air entraining additives (AIA) and hydration stabilizing additives (AEH). These authors explain that the function of air entrainers is related to the plasticity and workability of the material, while the stabilizers act to control cement hydration, inhibiting its reaction while the mortar is saturated with water.

In addition to the additives, it is necessary to stabilize the mortar at the end of each working day, preventing it from losing water to the environment, ensuring its main property. This stabilization is carried out through a water depth (2 or 3 cm) protecting the mortar that is stored in a suitable container at the work (MATOS, 2013). Once applied, it exhibits behavior similar to that of conventional mortars (MACIOSKI, 2014).

There is still little knowledge about the real properties of stabilized mortars, it is also highlighted that there is currently no Brazilian standard to regulate their characteristics or their performance, giving rise

to uncertainties about their quality (SANTOS, 2019).

Thus, new studies have emerged (SEQUEIRA & GHISLENE, 2020; KOFFS & VENDRUSCOLO, 2018; BELLEI et al.; 2015) that seek to improve the characteristics of products supplied to the construction market based on the use of pozzolanic materials in these mortars, thus aiming improve all the particularities of the product, whether fresh or hardened (LAURENTINO, 2019).

Kaolin is a material formed essentially by the mineral kaolinite and which is generally white or almost white. It is a material found in nature originated from sedimentary rocks, composed mainly of silica (SiO_2) and alumina (Al_2O_3) (AZERÊDO, 2012). The extraction and processing of this material generates large amounts of waste, contributing to the degradation of the environment. Barata (1998), Pera and Amrouz (1998) and Souza, P. (2003) analyzed the kaolin residue and verified that after the residue was ground and calcined it was possible to obtain a pozzolan with high reactivity for potland concrete and cement mortars.

In this context, the article proposes the use of kaolin residue, after passing through sieving and calcination, obtaining metakaolin (MK) as a pozzolanic material in stabilized mortars. Studies involving pozzolanic material in stabilized mortars are not widespread. Therefore, in this scenario, this article intends to evaluate the properties of these mortars with the use of this residue, verifying its behavior in the fresh state and its hardened properties.

MATERIALS

The mortars produced are composed of Portland cement, sand, metakaolin, water, hydration stabilizing additive and air-entraining additive. The materials were characterized in terms of physical, chemical and mineralogical aspects, as shown in table 1.

Table 1. Material characterization tests.

Analyze	Tests
Physics	Laser granulometry; Sieving granulometry; Especific mass; Unit mass; Specific Area (BET)
Chemistry	X-Ray Fluorescence (FRX).
Mineralogical	X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

Source: Own authorship (2022)

Table 2 presents the results of the physical analyzes performed on the materials used, with unit and specific masses taken from Araújo (2019). The specific area of Portland cement was also retained from Araújo (2019). The specific area of metakaolin was taken from Gaião (2019). The specific area was determined by the BET method. The two references used the same materials as the present study.

Table 2: Physical characteristics of materials

Material	Unit Mass (g/cm^3)	Specific Mass (g/cm^3)	Specific Area (cm^2/g)
Sand (S)	1.670	2.62	-
Portland cement (CP-V)	0.890	2.92	24800
Incorporating Additive of Air (IAA)	-	1.1	-

Hydration Stabilizing Additive (HSA)	-	1.140	-
Metakaolin (MK)	0.491	2.59	183000

Source: Own authorship (2022)

The unit mass of sand (S) was determined according to NBR NM 45 (ABNT, 2006). The unitary masses of Portland cement (CP-V), Metakaolin (MK) and were determined in the same way, however adapted with the use of a container of smaller volume than recommended by the standard.

The calcined kaolin residue was collected from the industries near Juazeirinho-PB and underwent a laboratory treatment process as carried out in Andrade (2019). Preparation included sieving and calcination. After this stage, the kaolin residue went to the second stage of the treatment, the calcination. The calcination took place in a muffle furnace, which was heated to a temperature of 700°C and remained there for 2 hours. The calcination time and chosen residencies were based on the works of Oliveira (2004) and Nóbrega (2007). After calcination, the oven was allowed to cool down gradually and then the material was removed and stored in a closed container. Henceforth, this calcined residue was called metakaolin (MK).

The specific mass of the sand was determined according to NBR NM 52 (ABNT, 2003). The specific mass tests of Portland Cement and Metakaolin were carried out based on NBR NM 23 (ABNT, 2000), using Le Chatelier's volumetric flask, in which the volume of a body is measured through the displacement of water.

METHODS

The preparation of the mortar samples included a reference mixture (without pozzolanic addition) and others containing the additions (metakaolin) with additions of up to 20% in relation to the binder mass.

The reference trace used in this study was 1:5.804 (binder: sand), a trace provided by local concrete producer Supermix Concreto SA, which sells this product in the city of Campina Grande-PB, which consisted of using a part of Portland cement to 5.804 of fine aggregate, 0.0044% of the IAA additive and 0.916% of the HSA additive, by mass. The mortar mixture procedure was performed according to NBR 16.541 (ABNT, 2016). The mixtures were stored in PVC containers, in a place protected from the sun and wind, with a water slide.

Table 3: Identification of the mixtures analyzed

Mortars	CP-V (g)	Sand (g)	MK (g)	IAA (g)	HSA (g)	Water (g)
REF	1312.47	7617.58	0	0.577	12.022	1273.1
10%MK	1312.47	7617.58	131.25	0.577	12.022	1443.7
20%MK	1312.47	7617.58	262.50	0.577	12.022	1456.8

Source: Own authorship (2022)

All mortar mixtures were molded in prismatic containers (4 x 4 x 16) cm according to current regulations. This molding took place for different stabilization times (0h and 48h) and the samples after hardening will be demolded and placed in wet curing until the age of 28 days, then proceeding with the analysis in the hardened state.

All mixtures were evaluated both in their fresh and hardened state. The properties evaluated in the fresh state are: workability, air content and fresh mass density. The workability consisted of the Flow Table test, according to NBR 13.276 (ABNT, 2016).

The determination of fresh mass and air content was carried out according to the procedures of NBR 13.278 (ABNT, 2005). In this test, the relationship between the volume and mass of fresh mortar was determined. This characteristic is directly linked to the yield of the ready-made mortar, in other words, the volume it yields for application. The equipment for carrying out these tests is available at the structures laboratory of the CW block (UFCG-Campina Grande).

For the study of the characteristics of the mortars in the hardened state, the following tests were carried out: mechanical resistance (compression), apparent mass density in accordance with the standards NBR 13279 (ABNT, 2005), NBR 13280 (ABNT, 2005), respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 (a) shows the granulometric curve of the sand, the limits of the usable and optimal zone of the fine aggregate according to NBR 7211 (ABNT, 2005). The Natural Sand is within the limits of the usable zone. For the MK, used in the study, laser granulometry was performed, the results of which were taken from the study by Oliveira (2019), which used the same materials. The method used was dry integrated dispersion with the CILAS 1090 model granulometer and the test was carried out at the Materials Laboratory - UFPB, João Pessoa-PB campus. Figure 1 (b) presents the granulometric curve obtained for the MK.

Figure 1: S and MK granulometric curve.

Source: Araújo (2019) and Oliveira (2019).

The chemical analysis of CP-V and MK were taken from the work of Laurentino (2019) and Oliveira (2019) and are shown in table 4. The authors performed the tests using X-ray fluorescence (FRX).

Table 4: Chemical composition by x-ray fluorescence (% by mass) of CP-V and MK.

	SiO_2	Al_2O_3	Fe_2O_3	CaO	MgO	K_2O	MnO	TiO_2	SO_3	SrO	Outros
CP-V	16.38	5.58	3.38	66.94	1.50	1.68	0.03	0.25	4.08	0.07	0.10
MK	65.03	31.37	0.69	-	-	1.41	-	-	0.21	0.06	0.019

Source: Adapted, Laurentino (2019) and Oliveira (2019).

When observing the results of the chemical analysis (Table 4), it can be seen that CP-V is within the requirements of standard NBR 5733 (1991). In relation to MK, according to NBR 12653 (2014), it is classified as class N pozzolanic material because it has percentages of $SiO_2 + Al_2O_3 + Fe_2O_3 = 97.09\% \geq 70\%$.

The consistency of the mortar depends directly on the amount of water present in the mixture. Thus, according to NBR 13276 (ABNT, 2016), a spreading index of 260 ± 5 mm was fixed for the analysis of the consistency of the mortars. Therefore, the amount of water was determined through trials until obtaining a value in this range. Figure 2 shows the spreading of the samples and figure 3 shows the fresh mass density and the entrained air content of the mortars.

Figure 2: Consistency of mortars.

Source: Own authorship (2022)

Figure 3: Fresh mass density and incorporated air content of the mortars.

Source: Own authorship (2022)

When analyzing figure 2, it is possible to notice the decrease in the consistency index of the mixtures with the increase of the stabilization time, reducing its workability, caused by a better arrangement of the particles, reducing the air incorporated in the mortar.

Another important point is the reduction of workability in the mixtures with metakaolin that were superior to the reference mortar. Thus, the reference mortar had a 4.21% decrease in its spread in 48 hours in relation to its spread in 0 hours, whereas the mortars with 10% and 20% metakaolin showed a decrease of 11.27% and 13.43%, respectively, of its scattering at 48 hours in relation to its scattering at 0 hours, this can be explained by the fact that metakaolin presents a finer granulometry, facilitating the reduction of the incorporated air.

According to the results obtained, figure 3, it is possible to see that the longer the stabilization time, the greater the specific mass and the lower the air content incorporated, in all mixtures it may have been caused by the reduction of void spaces generated. by the reduction of bubbles caused by the settlement of the mass in the empty spaces as described by Oliveira (2017).

In addition, it can be seen that the higher the percentage of metakaolin, the higher the specific mass and the lower the content of incorporated air, which can be explained due to a better arrangement of the voids in the mortars containing metakaolin.

With the collected data, it was possible to calculate the apparent mass density in the hardened state of the mortars, shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Density of the apparent mass of the mortars.

Source: Own authorship (2022)

According to the results obtained, figure 4, it is possible to notice an increase in the apparent mass of the mortars as the stabilization time increases. As expected, since the increase in the apparent specific mass occurs with the increase in the proportion of metakaolin in the mixture, as well as in the specific mass in the fresh state, which may also have been caused by a better arrangement, or filling, of the voids by the metakaolin which is a fine textured material.

With the collected data, it was possible to determine the axial compressive strength of the mortars shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Resistance to axial compression of mortars.

Source: Own authorship (2022)

In Figure 5, it is possible to verify an increase in the compressive strength of the mortars as a function of the stabilization time, with a greater resistance in the mortars with addition in relation to the one without addition in the time of 48 hours, also due to the loss of strength of the mortar. reference at that time.

Mixtures with 20% MK showed higher strength for 48 hours compared to mixtures with 0 hours, as expected, since mortars with metakaolin require more time for hydration, as they tend to have a slower hydration process.

CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded that the use of metakaolin (MK) as a pozzolanic material in stabilized mortars increases the water/binder ratio. The workability measured in the Flow Table showed a reduction in spreading in all mixtures, but the mixtures with metakaolin had a much more significant loss of consistency, reaching 13.43% against 4.21% of the reference samples.

As for the content of incorporated air and specific mass in the fresh hardened state, it was observed that there was a decrease in the incorporated air and an increase in the specific mass with the course of the stabilization time for all mixtures. However, due to the fineness of the metakaolin that filled the voids, the specific mass increased with the higher MK content.

Finally, regarding the axial compression strength, a longer stabilization time significantly increases the strength of the samples with the addition of metakaolin, but the reference samples showed, in general, a better resistance in the cure of 28 for a stabilization of 0 and 48 hours.

Concluding, therefore, that stabilized mortars containing addition of 10% and 20% of metakaolin in relation to cement, present satisfactory properties and can be used for laying.

REFERENCES

ANDRADE, L. B. Analysis of the properties of fresh and hardened mortars using kaolin residue. Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG). Campina Grande : n.n., 2019.

ARAÚJO, A. C. V. Influence of plasticizer additive and metakaolin on the technological properties of expanded vermiculite coating mortar. Completion of course work (graduation). Federal University of Campina Grande -UFCG, 2019.

BRAZILIAN ASSOCIATION OF TECHNICAL STANDARDS (ABNT). NBR 16541: Mortar for laying and covering walls and ceilings – Preparation of the mixture for testing. Rio de Janeiro, 2016.

_____. NBR NBR 16916: Fine aggregate - Determination of density and water absorption. Rio de Janeiro, 2021.

_____. NBR 16605: Portland cement and other powder materials – Determination of the specific mass. Rio de Janeiro, 2017.

_____. NBR 13280: Mortar for laying and covering walls and ceilings – Determination of the apparent mass density in the hardened state. Rio de Janeiro, 2005.

_____. NBR 13279: Mortar for laying and covering walls and ceilings – Determination of tensile strength in bending and compression. Rio de Janeiro, 2005.

_____. NBR 13278: Mortar for laying and covering walls and ceilings – determination of the mass density and the content of incorporated air. Rio de Janeiro, 2005.

_____. NBR 13276: Mortar for laying and covering walls and ceilings – determination of consistency index. Rio de Janeiro, 2016.

_____. NBR 13529: Inorganic mortar wall and ceiling coverings – Terminology. Rio de Janeiro, 2013.

_____. NBR 12653: Pozzolanic Materials — Requirements. Rio de Janeiro, 2014.

_____. NBR 7200: Execution of coating walls and ceilings with inorganic mortars - Procedure. Rio de Janeiro, 1998.

_____. NBR 5752: Pozzolanic materials – Determination of performance index with Portland cement at 28 days. Rio de Janeiro, 2014.

_____. NBR NM 248: Aggregates - Determination of granulometric composition. Rio de Janeiro, 2003.

_____. NBR NM 45: Aggregates – Determination of unit mass and void volume. Rio de Janeiro, 2006.

AZERÊDO, A. F. N. Study of kaolin residue in lime-based mortars regarding their fresh, hardened and microstructural properties. 230 f. Doctoral thesis in Civil Engineering. Graduate Program in Civil and Environmental Engineering. Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE). Recife PE. 2012

BARATA, M. S. High performance concrete in Pará: study of the technical and economic feasibility of producing high performance concrete with materials available in Belém through the use of silica fume and metakaolin additions. Dissertation (Master in Civil Engineering), UFRGS, Porto Alegre-RS, 1998.

BAUER, E. et al. Requirements for stabilized mortars for coating. In: BRAZILIAN SYMPOSIUM ON MORTAR TECHNOLOGY, 11., 2015, Porto Alegre. Proceedings of the Brazilian Symposium on Mortar Technology. Porto Alegre: SBTA, 2015.

BELLEI, P.; JANTSCH, A.C.A.; MOHAMAD, G.; RETZLAFF, G. N. Comparative Study of the Performance in the Fresh and Hardened State of Stabilized Mortars of 36H and 72H, 11., 2015, Porto Alegre. Proceedings of the Brazilian Symposium on Mortar Technology. Porto Alegre: SBTA, 2015.

BEZERRA, I.M.T.; et al. Application of rice husk ash in laying mortars. Brazilian Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Engineering (Agriambi), v. 15, no. 6, p. 639 – 645, 2011.

CARVALHO, C. M., (2016) Characterization of waste from the ceramic industry and its use in Portland cement mortars. 101 f. Thesis (Master's degree). Postgraduate Program in Materials Engineering. Federal University of Paraíba – UFPB, João Pessoa/PB, 2016.

CASALI, J.M.; et al. Evaluation of the properties of the fresh and hardened state of the stabilized mortar for coating. In: BRAZILIAN SYMPOSIUM ON MORTAR TECHNOLOGY, 14., 2017, São Paulo. Proceedings of the Brazilian Symposium on Mortar Technology. Sao Paulo: SBTA, 2017.

CARASEK, H. “Mortars”. In: Isaiah, G.C. (ed.). Civil Construction Materials and Principles of Materials Science and Engineering, São Paulo, IBRACON, pp. 892-944, 2010.

FERREIRA, K. Comparative study between conventional and industrialized mortars. 63 f. Course Completion Work (TCC). Federal Technological University of Paraná (UTFPR). Academic Department of Civil Construction – Civil Engineering. Campo Mourão, Paraná. 2016

GAIÃO, I. S. Light structural concrete containing expanded clay and mineral addition of metakaolin and ceramic brick residue. Course Completion Work (TCC). Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG). Campina Grande : n.n., 2019.

KOFFS, G.N.; VENDRUSCOLO, I. M. D. Analysis of the effect of mineral additions on the durability of stabilized mortars. 56 f. Course Completion Work (TCC). Federal Technological University of Paraná. Academic Department of Civil Construction (Civil Engineering). White Duck – RS. 2018

LAURENTINO, R. N. A. Study of stabilized mortar for laying with mineral addition of metakaolin. Course Completion Work (TCC). Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG). Campina Grande : n.n., 2019.

MACIOSKI, G. Evaluation of the behavior of stabilized mortars for coating, Federal University of Paraná, Curitiba, Paraná, 2014.

MATOS, P. R. D. Study of the use of stabilized mortar in structural masonry of concrete blocks. 73 f. Technological Center. Civil Engineering, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, 2013.

NÓBREGA, A. F. Potential of use of kaolin residues from Paraíba for the development of multipurpose mortars. 2007. Dissertation (Master in Urban Engineering), Federal University of Paraíba, João Pessoa-PB, 2007.

OLIVEIRA, V. C. Behavioral study of the formulation, requirements, and properties of stabilized coating mortars. 245 f. Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering of the Faculty of Technology. University of Brasilia Brasilia (UNB). Brasilia DF. 2017.

OLIVEIRA, M.P. Study of a calcined kaolin from the state of Paraíba as a partial replacement material for Portland cement. 2004. Dissertation (Master in Agricultural Engineering), UFCG, Campina Grande, 2004.

PAGNUSSAT, D.T.; VIDOR, D.; MASUERO, A. Evaluation of properties of stabilized mortars over time of use. In: Portuguese Congress of Mortars and Etics, p. 304-316. Coimbra, Portugal. 2012

PERA, J.; AMROUZ A. Development of Highly Reactive Metakaolin from Paper Sludge. *Advanced Cement Based Materials*, vol. 7, 1998.

ROCHA, A.K. et al. Mixed mortars for masonry using kaolin residue - Part I: mechanical behavior. *School of Mines Magazine*, v. 61, no. 4, p. 505–512, 2008.

ROMANO, R. C. O. Incorporation of air in cementitious materials applied in civil construction. 253 f. Doctoral thesis. Graduate Program in Civil Engineering. Polytechnic School of the University of São Paulo, University of São Paulo, São Paulo, 2013.

ROSENDE, P. S. O. Effect of Air Incorporated in Coating Mortars. 89 f. Masters dissertation. Graduate Program in Civil Construction (Civil Engineering). Federal University of Goiás (UFG). Goiania/GO, 2010.

SANTOS, C. L. L.; AGOSTINHO, G.M.; LYDIA, M.B.; et al. Analysis of fresh, hardened and microstructural properties of stabilized mortar. In: XIII Brazilian Symposium on Mortar Technology. *Anais do XIII SBTA*, p. 700-707. ISSN: 1984-8757. Goiânia-GO. 2019

SEQUEIRA, E.M.; GHISLENI, G. The influence of adding limestone filler in partial replacement of cement in stabilized mortar for wall and ceiling coverings. *Environmental Management & Sustainability Magazine*, v. 9, p. 20-38, 2020.

SINHORELLI, K. S. Study of the rheological and thermal properties of coating mortars containing mineral additions and vermiculite. 102 f. Thesis (Master's degree). Graduate Program in Civil and Environmental Engineering. Federal University of Paraíba – UFPB, João Pessoa/PB, 2019.

SOUZA, P. S. L. Verification of the influence of the use of high reactivity metakaolin on the mechanical properties of high strength concrete. 2003. Thesis (Doctorate in Civil Engineering) UFRG, Porto Alegre, 2003.

THOME, M.W.; SANTOS, M.S.C.; et al. Study of the influence of the water depth used in the storage of stabilized mortar. In: XIII Brazilian Symposium on Mortar Technology. *Anais do XIII SBTA*, p. 331-339. ISSN: 1984-8757. Goiânia-GO. 2019

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The work presented in this article was partially supported by the company Supermix Concreto SA and by the Scientific Initiation Program of the Federal University of Campina Grande – PB.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.